

Assessment of the Attitude of Youth towards Entrepreneurship: Evidence from Surkhet Nepal

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Abstract

The growth of entrepreneurial spirit is crucial for economic progress, which is why this topic of study has attracted significant attention recently. The knowledge youths acquire in entrepreneurship has a substantial influence on their impressions of this field. This study aims to assess youth's attitudes towards entrepreneurship. Furthermore, this study seeks to examine the influence of social networks, access to capital, education, government assistance policies, and creativity and risk-taking on the attitudes of young entrepreneurs. A descriptive and causal-comparative research design were employed in this study. A convenience sample was used to choose 150 young entrepreneurs (aged 20 to 35) from the Surkhet District. Data collection was conducted using a self-administered questionnaire. The IBM SPSS 26 software was utilized to conduct both descriptive and inferential analyses. The findings revealed that dimensions of the entrepreneurial attitude of youth including social networks, access to capital, education, government support policy, and creativity and risk-taking had positive and significant impacts on entrepreneurial attitude. The study has significant implications for economic development, community participation, education, support systems, and policy, all of which are crucial for building a dynamic entrepreneurial ecosystem among the young of Surkhet, Nepal.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial attitude, financial accessibility, social networks, youth's education, risk-taking, Surkhet, Nepal

Background of the Study

Entrepreneurial development is now particularly significant because it plays a crucial role in fostering economic growth (Naude, 2008). Entrepreneurs significantly contribute to a nation's economic growth. Teaching young people about entrepreneurship is essential for developing their mindset and attitudes toward starting their own businesses. Nowadays, entrepreneurship is seen as a key strategy for fostering economic growth and maintaining competitiveness amid globalization. Economically advanced nations such as Japan, the United States, and Germany illustrate how entrepreneurship fuels economic progress. For many young people, especially in developing and underdeveloped countries, the scarcity of job opportunities makes entrepreneurship a promising and supported career choice.

Many economists have emphasized the importance of entrepreneurship in driving economic development. Smith's perspective, as noted by Taneja S. and Gupta S.L (2006), highlights this role since 1776. Schumpeter (1934) identified entrepreneurship as a key factor of production, underscoring its significance in fostering economic growth. Leff (1979) and Harper (1991) also recognized entrepreneurship as the fourth factor of production, crucial for discovering new opportunities that lead to comprehensive economic advancement. Additionally, Leibenstein (1968) pointed out its role in creating new ventures and sustaining existing ones.

Shapero (1985) saw entrepreneurship as a catalyst for diversity, innovation, development, and personal independence within society. It plays a vital role in furthering social progress by generating job opportunities and fostering economic prosperity. Misra and Puri (2010) viewed entrepreneurship development as a strategy for enhancing human resources, boosting creativity, competence, and overall fulfillment. Desai (2009) pointed out that entrepreneurship plays a crucial role in a country's economic development. Santi and Rajeshkumar (2011) emphasized that a nation's economic progress hinges on its industrial growth, which relies on the entrepreneurial skills of its people. Mehta (2013) also described the relationship between entrepreneurship and the economy as interconnected, where one influences the other. In the current era of Industry 4.0, online entrepreneurship is increasingly seen as a vital driver of innovative growth and national development, as highlighted by Pham et al. (2023).

In Nepal, political instability often leads people to seek secure jobs or emigrate instead of starting their own businesses. Despite these challenges, the country's business and industrial

sectors have grown significantly. Industries like Banking, Telecommunications, FMCGs, and Hotels have flourished thanks to favorable market conditions. Urbanization and a growing interest in international exposure have rapidly changed people's lifestyles and preferences. This shift creates opportunities for small and medium-sized enterprises to address market gaps and meet new demands, resulting in a noticeable increase in small businesses and entrepreneurial activity in Nepal. To achieve the goal of reducing poverty by creating jobs and launching industries that generate employment for young people, the Industry Ministry and National Youth Council signed an agreement on December 27, 2017. This agreement aims to enhance youth participation in the nation's socio-economic transformation. By focusing on agriculture, forestry, tourism, and service-oriented industries, it seeks to offer opportunities for disadvantaged and unemployed youths to improve their circumstances and contribute to Nepal's entrepreneurial landscape. Additionally, interest-free loans will be provided to help young people purchase necessary materials and technology for entrepreneurship programs and development. On December 27, 2017, the Industry Ministry and National Youth Council agreed to promote youth employment and socio-economic transformation through agriculture, forestry, tourism, and service industries. They will provide interest-free loans to help disadvantaged and unemployed youths acquire materials and technology for entrepreneurship.

The lack of job opportunities in the formal market is a significant factor behind the high unemployment rate among young people. Despite this, many have the potential to start their own businesses. But do they have a positive attitude towards entrepreneurship? Are they interested in pursuing a business career? While numerous studies have explored what makes an entrepreneur and the obstacles they face, none have specifically examined the intentions and attitudes of young people in Nepal towards starting their own businesses. This study aims to uncover the factors that contribute to successful youth startups in the Surkhet district. It will also identify the specific needs of young aspiring entrepreneurs.

Review of Literature

Shapero and Sokol (1982) suggest that attitude plays a crucial role in shaping one's inclination towards entrepreneurship, particularly concerning how feasible and desirable a venture appears to be. They highlight various dimensions of entrepreneurial mindset. It's commonly believed that individuals who value a significant level of independence in their lives tend to exhibit

more entrepreneurial behaviors. In his 1990 study, Douglas E. explored how a person's intention to start their own business is influenced by their attitudes towards income, independence, risk, and work effort. The study found that individuals who have a more positive view of independence and risk are more likely to have a strong desire to become entrepreneurs.

Van Wyk et al. (2003) examined how entrepreneurial mindset correlates with various personal and professional factors among a group of professionals, comprising pharmacists and accountants. They assessed personality traits such as Type A behavior, locus of control, career aspirations, and self-perception, along with work-related aspects like job satisfaction and engagement. Their analysis revealed significant links between entrepreneurial attitude and these factors, with multiple regression indicating key predictors for entrepreneurial attitudes. In a study conducted by Veciana et al. (2005), the attitudes of university students towards entrepreneurship and starting businesses in Catalonia and Puerto Rico were evaluated and contrasted. Their research indicated a generally favorable view of entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship. However, while the perception of entrepreneurship was positive, the belief in its feasibility was less strong, with only a minority expressing definite intentions to initiate new ventures.

Evan (2005) examined how entrepreneurial attitude and self-confidence influence a person's intention to start a business. Using a seven-point scale (from very unlikely to very likely), the study measured students' intentions across eight different entrepreneurial behaviors. The findings revealed that students who value higher income, greater independence, and ownership tend to have stronger entrepreneurial intentions. Stemphone and Melvin researched 145 retired military officers from the Singapore Armed Forces to understand what drives mid-career individuals to start their own businesses.

Schwarz et al. (2009) explored what motivates students to pursue entrepreneurship, using Ajzen's theory of planned behavior and Autio's intention model to develop a comprehensive framework. This model includes three main factors: general attitudes (towards money, change, and competitiveness), attitudes toward entrepreneurship, and perceptions of university support and regional startup ecosystems. Through an electronic survey and multiple linear regression analysis, they assessed attitudes, environmental perceptions, and control variables (such as age, gender, and field of study). The results showed that, except for competitiveness, all other attitudes significantly influenced entrepreneurial intentions. While university support was found to impact students'

interest in entrepreneurship, other environmental factors did not show a significant effect on their entrepreneurial intentions.

Packham et al. (2010) explored the effect of enterprise education on entrepreneurial attitudes among students in higher education institutions in France, Germany, and Poland. They found that this type of education positively influenced the entrepreneurial attitudes of French and Polish students, but had a negative impact on male German students. Interestingly, female students generally felt they benefited more from the course, although the positive impact on entrepreneurial attitude was more pronounced among male students. Santhi and Rajeshkumar (2011) argued that individual attitudes towards entrepreneurship play a crucial role in the likelihood of becoming an entrepreneur. Despite the challenge of measuring this effect, they found that positive attitudes towards entrepreneurship are linked to high levels of entrepreneurial activity, suggesting that entrepreneurship fosters economic growth by connecting innovation with the market.

Kgagara (2011) examined young people's attitudes towards entrepreneurship and found that many respondents believed that academic institutions should promote entrepreneurship, with a significant number expressing a desire to start their own businesses. Although students had a positive view of entrepreneurship, they lacked a clear understanding of its profile, ethics, and educational requirements. They were neutral about the risks involved and the necessity of education for entrepreneurship, and many believed they could earn more by working for others. Ali et al. (2011) studied the entrepreneurial attitudes of potential entrepreneurs in Pakistan, surveying 480 management students from six public universities. They discovered that factors such as demographics, university attended, parental income, and profession influenced entrepreneurial attitudes, with no significant gender differences observed.

Talaş et al. (2013) studied the key demographic elements shaping the entrepreneurial aspirations of 638 undergraduate students, considering entrepreneurship as a viable career path at a four-year public university in Turkey. Their findings underscored the considerable impact of factors such as the composition of the current faculty, the nature of the high school attended, and the household income on the students' inclination towards entrepreneurship.

Adebayo and Kavos (2016) in their study examined the attitudes of African youth towards starting new businesses and entrepreneurship. Using both surveys and interviews participants were

contacted via social media. The results indicate that African youth have positive attitudes toward entrepreneurship, are active in this area, and are willing to take risks to achieve self-sufficiency.

The study also emphasizes the importance of entrepreneurship education to enhance innovative start-ups in Africa. Ndungub and Anyieni (2019) investigated the attitudes of youth towards entrepreneurship in public technical institutions in Nakuru County, Kenya. It looked into factors affecting these attitudes, including personal traits and external influences like culture, education, and environment. The study found that parents and guardians had a significant impact on students' choice of courses. Although many respondents' families owned businesses, most students were not involved in them. Factors such as lack of finances, complex business licensing procedures, and high loan interest rates negatively influenced students' views on entrepreneurship. Nwankwo & Kanyangale's 2020 study explored how gender role orientation and self-confidence influence the desire to start a business, based on responses from 350 students. The research found notable differences in gender roles and established a strong link between self-confidence and entrepreneurial ambitions.

Saleh et al. (2021) analyzed the entrepreneurial attitude among youth in Yemen where findings reveal a moderate positive attitude towards entrepreneurship. Interestingly it is found that there's no significant difference in attitudes based on age, gender, residence, education, or parents' education. This suggests a growing inclination towards entrepreneurship due to economic conditions, lack of government development initiatives, and the youth's desire for stable employment, whether in industries or through their own enterprises.

The study of Sharma et al. (2022) investigated the perceptions of Management students in Chhattisgarh, towards entrepreneurship. Results suggest that students have increasing awareness of available resources and many students demonstrated familiarity with start-up concepts and government initiatives, indicating a solid understanding of the entrepreneurial landscape. This research offers insights into the shifting mindset of students, highlighting their favorable outlook on entrepreneurship and willingness to partake in entrepreneurial activities where findings are relevant for educational institutions, policymakers, and stakeholders interested in fostering a more entrepreneurial atmosphere among youth. This research of Bagis et al. (2023) investigated the factors shaping entrepreneurial intentions and awareness among Turkish university students. Through the analysis employing various statistical methods, it reveals that personal attitudes,

perceived behavioral control, and the need for achievement significantly influence students' entrepreneurial aspirations and awareness in Turkey, Poland, and Kosovo. Moreover, study shows that personal attitudes and perceived behavioral control act as mediators in the relationship between the need for achievement and entrepreneurial intention and awareness.

A close perusal of the existing literature indicates that entrepreneurial attitude orientation studies were extensively carried out in other countries all over the world but there has been little effort to study the entrepreneurial attitude of youth in Nepal, notably in the Surkhet district. Further, the current studies were related to the analysis of the entrepreneurial intention of the students enrolled in courses like engineering and management. The predominant youths from different backgrounds were not studied in depth. Hence, the current study is expected to fill the research gap.

Development of Conceptual Framework of the Study

Independent variable

Dependent variable

Figure1: Conceptual Framework of the Study

Development of Hypotheses

Social Networks

Family background significantly influences an individual's entrepreneurial intentions. Davidson (195) found that a substantial percentage of entrepreneurs had parents who were self-employed, highlighting the positive impact of role models. Growing up surrounded by entrepreneurship can shape perceptions, making it seem more achievable and desirable. Family expectations and role models, particularly parents, play a crucial role in shaping entrepreneurial aspirations. Social

norms that support entrepreneurship further strengthen these intentions. Krueger et al. (2012) note, however, that an external locus of control can lessen the impact of social norms. Strong social connections also provide valuable resources, such as information and social capital, which are essential for starting a business.

Hypothesis 1: Social networks have a positive influence on the entrepreneurial attitude of youth.

Access to Capital

A significant obstacle for entrepreneurs is securing sufficient funding for their ventures. Peng (2009) highlights the challenge of limited financial resources for small and medium-sized enterprises, hindering their ability to capitalize on opportunities. Access to capital is crucial for the success of entrepreneurial endeavors. Shujahat (2004) emphasizes how restricted access to capital and inflexible financial systems hinder business innovation, particularly in developing economies. Entrepreneurs often rely on personal savings, family networks, and informal credit, despite potential drawbacks like high-interest rates.

Hypothesis 2: Access to capital has a positive influence on the entrepreneurial attitude of youth in Surkhet district.

Education

Entrepreneurship education aims to encourage individuals to consider entrepreneurship as a career path or a way to contribute to their communities. It achieves this by fostering an entrepreneurial mindset, showcasing career opportunities, and teaching essential business skills. Lakovleva (2011) highlights how entrepreneurship education equips individuals with the knowledge, skills, and analytical abilities needed to identify and seize opportunities. Okafor (2010) views it as a form of human capital investment that prepares individuals to launch new ventures. A study by Peterman and Kennedy (2003) demonstrated that an enterprise education program positively influenced students' perceptions of entrepreneurship, making them view starting a business as more desirable and feasible.

Hypothesis 3: *Perceived entrepreneurial Education has a positive influence on the entrepreneurial attitude of youth.*

Government Support Policy

Government plays a crucial role in promoting entrepreneurship by creating a supportive environment for businesses to thrive. Nkya (2003) emphasizes the importance of institutions that incentivize creativity and risk-taking among entrepreneurs. This involves implementing supportive policies, fostering a culture that embraces innovation, and simplifying business regulations. Many potential entrepreneurs hesitate to start businesses due to unfavorable environments, complex regulations, or lack of support. This highlights the significance of contextual factors in either encouraging or hindering entrepreneurship. Therefore, establishing institutions that recognize the value of the private sector and entrepreneurship is essential for the success of both new and existing businesses.

Hypothesis 4: Perceived Government support and favorable regulation promote the entrepreneurship intention of youth.

Creativity and Risk-taking

Successful entrepreneurs often possess a distinct set of traits. Phan (2002) identifies a strong achievement drive, risk tolerance, self-confidence, internal locus of control, creativity, and innovation as common characteristics. Similarly, Buang (2011) highlights self-confidence, opportunity recognition, risk-taking, creativity, and innovation as key entrepreneurial qualities often found in individuals who choose self-employment. Lee and Peterson (2000) further emphasize self-efficacy, innovativeness, proactiveness, autonomy, risk-taking, and competitiveness as crucial elements of an entrepreneurial orientation. They note that these traits are particularly pronounced in students from developing countries like Indonesia, driven by challenges such as competition, unemployment, and poverty.

Hypothesis 5: Creativity and risk-taking characteristics have a positive influence on the entrepreneurial intention of youth in the Surkhet district.

Research Methods

This study employs a survey method with both descriptive and inferential statistical approaches to understand the attitudes of youths in the Surkhet district towards entrepreneurship. The primary objective is to analyze how various factors influence entrepreneurial attitudes among young people in this region. The organization, analysis, and interpretation of data collected from respondents enable the successful accomplishment of the study's goals.

To systematically explore the effects of six independent variables—social networks, government policy, creativity and risk-taking, education, and access to capital—on the dependent variable, entrepreneurial attitude, this study collects data using a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire measures various factors on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly agree) to 5 (strongly disagree). The responses are then analyzed using statistical software.

The purpose of the self-administered survey was to collect the respondents' responses to a standardised questionnaire are utilised to get the primary data. The questionnaire will be used to help with in-person interviews with the respondents. The survey was divided into three sections. Demographic and basic information is included in the first section. The remark about the measures of the independent variables and the dependent variables was included in the second section. Statements about important determinants and obstacles to entrepreneurship were included in the third section of the survey. Convenience sampling was used to choose the respondents. It was emphasised that participation was entirely optional and unobligated. We only needed the demographic information for statistical purposes.

Results and Discussion

4.1. Descriptive Statistics

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation
Social Networks	3.3	0.99
Access to Capital	3.57	0.90
Education	3.94	0.64
Government Support Policy	3.97	0.59
Creativity and Risk-taking	3.75	0.89
Entrepreneurial Attitude	3.33	1.28

Source: Survey Data 2024

The descriptive analysis of various factors influencing youth attitudes towards entrepreneurship reveals insightful statistics. Firstly, the variable of Social Network quantifies the breadth of an individual's social connections, with a mean value of 3.3 indicating an average level of influence, while the standard deviation of 0.99 underscores the variability in responses around this mean. Access to Capital is gauged by its mean score of 3.57, reflecting the perceived ease or difficulty in obtaining financial resources for entrepreneurial ventures, with a standard deviation of 0.90 indicating response diversity. Education, with a mean value of 3.94 and a standard deviation of 0.64, captures perceptions of its role in entrepreneurship, reflecting the level of educational attainment or access to resources. Government Support Policy, with a mean score of 3.97 and a standard deviation of 0.59, measures perceived effectiveness in fostering entrepreneurship through policies and programs. Creativity and Risk-taking, assessed with a mean of 3.75 and a standard deviation of 0.89, encapsulate attitudes towards innovation and risk tolerance in entrepreneurial pursuits. Finally, the Dependent Variable, Entrepreneurial Attitude, with a mean value of 3.33 and a standard deviation of 1.28, represents the average attitude score among youth, highlighting variability in attitudes toward entrepreneurship.

4.2. Correlation Analysis

Table 2

Correlation Analysis

Variables	SN	AC	ED	GSP	CR	EA
SN	1					
AC	.537**	1				
ED	.445**	.445**	1			
GSP	.462**	.462**	.462**	1		
CR	.362**	.362**	.362**	.362**	1	
EA	.444**	.444**	.444**	.444**	.444**	1

Note: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

SN = Social Networks, AC = Access to Capital, ED = Education, GSP = Government Support Policies, CR = Creativity and Risk-taking, and EA = Entrepreneurial Attitude.

Source: Survey Data 2024

This correlation analysis, presented in Table 2, explores the relationships between different variables related to attitudes toward entrepreneurship. Each cell in the table represents the correlation coefficient between two variables. For instance, the correlation coefficient between Social Network (SN) and Access to Capital (AC) is 0.537**, indicating a moderate positive correlation between these two variables. Similarly, the correlation coefficient between Social Networks and Education (ED) is 0.445**, suggesting a moderate positive correlation as well. Overall, the table reveals significant positive correlations between various factors. For example, there are moderate positive correlations between Social Networks, Access to Capital, Education, Government Support Policies, Creativity and Risk-taking, and Entrepreneurial Attitude, with correlation coefficients ranging from 0.362 to 0.537. This analysis provides valuable insights into the interrelationships among different factors influencing attitudes towards entrepreneurship among youth, highlighting potential areas of focus for interventions or further research.

4.3. Regression Analysis

Regression analysis is a statistical method used in statistical modelling to estimate the relationship between variables. When the relationship between a dependent variable and independent variables is the main focus, it contains a variety of modelling and analysis techniques. The overage relationship between two or more variables in terms of the initial unit of data is measured mathematically by regression analysis. Finding out more about the link between a number of independent or predictor variables and a dependent or criterion variable is the main goal of multiple regression analysis. Entrepreneurial mentality is the dependent variable in this study, and familiarity and social network, access to cash, education, government support and policy, innovation, and risk-taking are the independent variables.

The line of regression is $Y=A+BX$

“Multiple Regression Model”

$$“\hat{Y} = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \beta_5X_5 + e_i.”$$

“Where,

\hat{Y} = entrepreneurial attitude (dependent variable)

X_1 = familiarity and social network, X_2 = access to capital, X_3 = education, X_4 = government support and policy, X_5 = creativity and risk taking

α = Constant,

β_i = Coefficient of the slope of regression model

e_i = Error term”

Where A is constant and B is the regression coefficient. A measure of change Y per unit change in X. If 1 unit increases in familiarity and social network, the entrepreneurial attitude will also increase.

Table 3*“Regression Analysis- Model Summary”*

Model	R	Adjusted square	Std. error of estimate
1	.717 ^a	.514	.30127

a. Predictors: (constant), social networks, access to capital, education, government support policy, creativity and risk-taking.

Source: Survey Data 2024

Model summary indicates the R-square also known as coefficient of determination which can help in explaining variance. The value of R-square value as evident from above Table is 0.514 which means 51.4% variation in entrepreneurial attitude is explained by variable consisting of, familiarity and social network, access to capital, education, government support and policy, creativity and risk taking in Surkhet district. However, the remaining 48.6% (100%-51.4%) is still unexplained in this research. In other words, there are other additional variables that are important in explaining attitude of youth towards entrepreneurship in Surkhet district that have not been considered in this research.

Similarly, adjusted R-square is 0.51 which means 51% variation in entrepreneurial attitude is explained by familiarity and social network, access to capital, education, government support and policy, and creativity and risk taking of entrepreneurial attitude in Surkhet district after adjusting degree of freedom (df). This shows average relationship between all independent variables and dependent variable. Model summary also indicates the standard error of the estimate of 0.30127 which shows the variability of the observed value of factors influencing the entrepreneurial attitude of youths in Surkhet district from the regression line is 0.30127 units.

Table 4*ANOVA Test*

Model	Sum of square	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	9.779	5	1.956	21.547	.000
Residual	9.258	144	.096		
Total	19.036	149			

Dependent Variable: entrepreneurial attitude

b. Predictors: (constant), social networks, access to capital, education, government support policy, creativity and risk-taking.

Source: Survey Data 2024

Based on ANOVA, the p-value is 0.000 which is lesser than the alpha value. Therefore, the model is a good predictor of the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. As a result, the independent variables familiarity and social network, access to capital, education, government support and policy, creativity, and risk-taking aspect of entrepreneurial attitude in Surkhet district are significant in explaining the variable in youth's entrepreneurial attitude.

Table 5*Regression Coefficients*

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. error	Beta		
Constant	0.53	0.19		2.83	.006
Social Networks	0.22	0.05	0.36	4.63	.000
Access to Capital	0.11	0.06	0.15	1.75	.008
Education	0.12	0.05	0.21	2.61	.007
Government Support Policy	0.06	0.04	0.11	1.38	.009
Creativity and risk-taking	0.16	0.05	0.26	2.99	.003

Dependent Variable: entrepreneurial attitude

Source: Survey Data 2024

Taking five dimensions of the entrepreneurial attitude of youth including social network, access to capital, education, government support and policy, creativity, and risk-taking as independent variables (X1, X2, X3, X4, and X5) and entrepreneurial attitude as the dependent variable, the model is constructed with the equation as below:

$$\hat{Y} = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + e_i.$$

Based on the coefficients, the regression equation for the entrepreneurial attitude can be written as:

$$\hat{Y} = 0.532 + 0.220X_1 + 0.112X_2 + 0.12X_3 + 0.061X_4 + 0.163X_5.$$

Regression coefficients of familiarity and social network, access to capital, education, government support, and policy, creativity and risk-taking are 0.22, 0.112, 0.12, 0.061, and 0.163 respectively in entrepreneurial attitude.

Table 5 also shows that all independent variables have significant results since their respective p-values are less than the level of significance ($P < 0.01$).

Discussion

The results of the study have shown a positive relationship between independent variable (familiarity and social network, access to capital, education, government support and policies, and creativity and risk taking) and dependent variable (entrepreneurial attitude). The youth in Surkhet district have agreed that variable like familiarity and social network, access to capital, education, government support and policies, and creativity and risk taking plays a vital role in entrepreneurship attitude/ intention. As the competition has increased and business environment is dynamic and challenging, so all the independent variable in order to enhance entrepreneurial attitude, have to ensure that there is positive relation with dependent variable. Youths are becoming concerned about the different variables which includes familiarity and social network, access to capital, education, government support and policies, and creativity and risk taking as mentioned in this study. The regression analysis result showed that independent variable has positive impact on dependent variable as $R^2 = 51.4\%$ therefore it is necessary to pay attention towards this element of the attitude. Different statistical tools such as correlation tests are used depending upon the nature of data collected. Table 5.2 summarizes the hypotheses testing of the study. All the tested hypotheses are significant at a 1% level of significance. Thus, independent variables such as familiarity and social network, access to capital, education, government support and policies, and creativity and risk-taking have significant influences on the entrepreneurial attitude of youths in Surkhet district.

Harun Sesen (2013) provides confirmation for the findings, indicating that the entrepreneurial personality qualities that received the highest scores were innovativeness and industriousness. Their mindset was seen to have been positively impacted by family support and the availability of cash, but infrastructure, finance, and technological constraints were found to be impeding their potential. Among the variables that were shown to have an average impact on young people's attitudes towards entrepreneurship programmes were social ones.

Conclusions and Implications

These days, many countries are actively encouraging small and medium-sized businesses to create jobs for their growing young populations and stimulate economic growth. Research

consistently shows that these enterprises play a crucial role in achieving national development goals. Nepal is also prioritizing its small business sector, evident from the establishment of a dedicated Directorate under the Ministry of Commerce and Industry to support SMEs. This study specifically examines how young people in Surkhet district view entrepreneurship, emphasizing areas where the Nepalese government can foster a more entrepreneurial mindset and intentions among its youth.

In this study, we examined what shapes young people's views on entrepreneurship in Surkhet district. We looked at several key factors: familiarity and social connections, access to funding, education quality, government policies and support, and the ability to innovate and take risks. The findings clearly show that each of these factors significantly impacts how young people perceive entrepreneurship. Therefore, families, communities, government officials, policymakers, and educators should work together to leverage these factors effectively. By doing so, we can cultivate a more positive outlook on entrepreneurship among the youth of Surkhet district, ultimately fostering an environment where entrepreneurial aspirations can thrive.

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